

Degeneracy, Average Occupancy and Microstates in Statistical Mechanics Part II

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In Part II we examine how information may be used to define physical distribution functions. In particular, we argue that a mathematical function may be equivalent to certain pieces of information. For example, for elastic two body scattering $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$. Thus e_i is one piece of information in the problem. A second piece is the distribution function $n(e_i/T)$ where T is a parameter. A third piece of information is that $n(e_i)n(e_j) = n(e_i + e_j)$ or reaction balance: $n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4)$. These three pieces of information lead to the result: $\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ (AA) Thus we argue that the function $\exp(-e_i/T)$ may be thought of in terms of (AA).

Interestingly, we argue, (AA) is exactly of the form of a maximization of the function $-n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))$ subject to the constraint $e_i n(e_i)$. Why should maximization come into play if one has three pieces of information which already solve the problem? $n(e_i)$ is proportional to a probability for large N i.e. $n(e_i) = Np(e_i)$. Given probabilities, one may consider repeated trials i.e. N of them for N very large. In the large N limit one expects e_i to be associated with a probability $p(e_i)$ [power $Np(e_i)$]. Each trial of N events is a microstate and has the same probability, thus the microstates are permutations of each other. The probability should be $1/\{\text{number of permutations}\}$. This still does not define $n(e_i)$ if one writes: $1/\{\text{number of permutations}\} = 1/\{N!/\text{Product over } i n(e_i)!\}$ with the constraint that $\text{Sum over } i e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}$. The constraint term shows that e_i is one piece of information. One may take \ln of $1/\{\text{number of permutations}\}$ in order to have a sum of terms instead of a product i.e. $-\text{Sum over } i \ln(n(e_i)!)$. The idea from the first set of 3 information pieces that $\ln(n(e_i))$ should be associated with e_i is identical to maximizing $\ln(n(e_i)!)$ with respect to $n(e_i)$. Thus the function $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is associated with the maximization of removed information $n(e_i)!$ (because $n(e_i)!$ is in the denominator of $N!/\text{Product over } i n(e_i)!$).

The second example we consider is the relaxation of both a fixed E_{total} and N i.e. constraints $\text{Sum over } i n(e_i) = N_{\text{ave}}$ and $\text{Sum over } i e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}$. If one uses $\exp(-(E - uN)/T)$, a function which arose from the three pieces of information (or in other ways, for example from the constraints $\text{Sum over } i e_i n(e_i)$ and $\text{Sum over } i n(e_i)$), and considers E and N in terms of single particle values i.e. $E = \text{Sum over } i e_i n$ and $N = \text{Sum over } i n$ (in i) then for a fixed e_i , one may sum over n . This means one considers something special about the level e_i i.e. there is some information linked to a level e_i which is not present in the simple Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution or in the simple reaction balance $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and $n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4)$. (This special information, however, must correspond to actual information which appears in nature.)

Given that $\exp(-e_i/T)$ is linked to the constraint $\text{Sum over } i e_i n(e_i)$ and also to maximization permutations, one may guess that the two constraints: $\text{Sum over } i e_i n(e_i)$ and $\text{Sum over } i n(e_i)$ correspond to an $\exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ which in turn is also linked to some kind of permutations. Since one sums of n for a given e_i , it seems one considers probabilities of placing more than one particle in each energy level, with a product factor $\exp(-(e_i - u)/T)$ each time one adds another particle to e_i (in the boson case). This is an extra piece of information and may be linked with the maximization of permutations within a state e_i with g_i degenerate boxes. Thus instead of simply removing information $n(e_i)!$ in the denominator of a permutation expression, one may be trying to maximize information in the numerator through an expression $(a n(e_i) + b)!$ where a and

b are constants. Thus, sums of products of $\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$ factors may be ultimately linked to functions of the form: $(a n(e_i) + b)! / n(e_i)!$. This we argue is why the grand canonical distribution produces results identical to the maximization of permutations within energy levels e_i with degeneracies of g_i . The factor $(e_i-u)/T$ in $\exp(-(e_i-u)/T)$ from the grand canonical partition function is identical to $d/d n(e_i)$ of the two constraints $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$ and $\sum_i n(e_i)$ used in any maximization problem.

Information and Functional Form

We argue that a functional form may be directly associated with certain information. For example, consider the case of elastic two body scattering $e_1+e_2 = e_3+e_4$. Single particle energy e_i is a piece of important information. One also assumes an $n(e_i)$ function describing the number of particles with energy e_i . Finally, a third crucial piece of information is that:

$$n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3) n(e_4) \quad ((1))$$

for reaction balance to occur. One may see that information is being removed in the sense that for any $e_i+e_j = e_1+e_2$, $n(e_i)n(e_j) = n(e_1)n(e_2)$. Taking \ln of ((1)) to convert into a sum yields:

$$\ln[n(e_i)] = -e_i/T \quad ((2)) \quad (\text{This ultimately yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution } \exp(-e_i/T).$$

One may notice that $-e_i/T$ is equivalent to: $d/dn(e_i) (-e_i/T n(e_i))$. Thus $-e_i/Tn(e_i)$ is like a constraint term in a maximization problem. What, however, should be maximized? We argued above that one only needs three pieces of information to obtain $\exp(-e_i/T)$. If one has a problem with more information, it needs to be removed to obtain the same $\exp(-e_i/T)$. A constraint in the form of $-e_i n(e_i)$ brings in one piece of information and the assumption of an $n(e_i)$, the second piece. The third piece of information is that $\ln(n(e_i))$ must be associated with e_i .

$$\text{Given } n(e_i), \text{ one may assume that for large } N: n(e_i) = N p(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

This suggests a set of N (very large) trials leading to a microstate result. Even though one does not know the exact order of e_i results in this microstate, there should be $N p(e_i)$, e_i states. Thus the probability of the microstate is:

$$\text{Microstate probability} = \text{Product over } i p(e_i)^{N p(e_i)} \quad ((4))$$

Each microstate has the same probability and so one has permutations of various e_i results. Thus:

$$\text{Microstate probability} = 1 / \{ \text{number of permutations} \} = 1 / \{ N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)! \} \quad ((5))$$

At this point $n(e_i)$ is completely unknown. How may one solve for it? It seems one may use an informational argument. One may assume the constraint $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$ which yields the e_i piece of information upon taking $d/dn(e_i)$. from the first approach which together with the existence of $n(e_i)$ yields two pieces of information. The third piece of information is that $\ln(n(e_i))$

is proportional to e_i . $d/dn(e_i)$ is linked with a maximization process and taking \ln of Microstate probability and maximizing yields the direct link of:

$$d/d n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)!) - 1/T d/dn(e_i) e_i n(e_i) = 0$$

$$d/dn(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)!) = \{ \ln\{[n(e_i)+1]\} - \ln(n(e_i)!) \} / 1 = \ln(n(e_i)+1) \approx \ln(n(e_i)) \text{ for } n(e_i) \gg 1 \quad ((6))$$

Alternatively, one may use Stirling's approximation for $\ln(n(e_i)!)$.

This yields $\exp(-e/T)$. Thus the form $\exp(-e/T)$ is associated with certain information and is directly linked to a maximized $-\ln(n(e_i)!)$ form subject to a constraint $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$.

The Grand Canonical Partition Function

Consider the situation for which one has two constraints:

$$E_{\text{total}} \approx E_{\text{ave}} = \sum_i e_i n(e_i) \quad ((7a)) \text{ and } N_{\text{total}} \approx N_{\text{ave}} = \sum_i n(e_i)$$

$$((7b))$$

One may consider a fixed E_{total} and N and take a set of states with E_1, N_1 with weights of $\exp(-(E_1 - uN_1)/T)$. It may be shown (1) that this leads to a sharp distribution about E_{total}, N . Thus one might think of $\exp(-(E_1 - uN_1)/T)$ as being a mathematical approximation which allows one to relax the requirement of exact E_{total} and N . The two results, ((7a)) and ((7b)), however, show that this approach is also directly linked to some kind of maximization with ((7a)) and ((7b)) being constraints. For the single particle piece, $\exp(-(e_i - u)n/T)$ one has a $\ln(n(e_i))$ in the problem and the two constraints. If one considers a specific state e_i in $\exp(-(E_1 - uN_1)/T)$, one may sum over n i.e.

$$\sum_n \exp(-(e_i - u)n/T) \quad ((8))$$

What is happening in this case? One is assigning extra information to a single state e_i by computing a sum of a kind of relative set of probabilities. This assumes one may have any number of particles in state e_i , a property which applies to bosons. Thus the result ((8)) should be linked to some kind of expression of $\ln(a n(e_i) + b)$ terms (a, b constants) which in turn may be linked to $d/dn(e_i)$ of $\ln(a n(e_i) + b)!$ terms. The factorial suggests an expression of total arrangements within a single level e_i . Thus it seems one tries to place as many particles as possible into state e_i from ((8)), but at the same time this result should be equivalent to some kind of degenerate arrangement calculation. What degenerate arrangements exist within a single state e_i ? It would seem none unless there are degeneracies within a single energy state such as the position of momentum vectors which have the same magnitude etc. In particular, ((8)) suggests that one try to place as many particles as possible in a state e_i . In other words, there is a probabilistic benefit to having more particles in e_i as long as the constraints $\sum_i e_i n(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}$ and $\sum_i n(e_i) = N_{\text{ave}}$ are not violated.

In other words, the simple three piece information picture of two body scattering with $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ and $n(e_1)n(e_2)=n(e_3)n(e_4)$ no longer holds. There is an extra piece of information which suggests there exists an enhancement factor linked with placing as many particles in each state as possible. This enhancement factor may be calculated.

We first start with ((8)) and sum it using the rules of a geometric series. Then:

$$\ln(Z_{(ei) \text{ piece}}) = \ln\left(\frac{1}{1-\exp(-(e-u)/T)}\right) \quad ((9))$$

To find $n(e_i)$ one uses: $-T \frac{d}{de(i)} \ln(Z)$ (see (2) page 187)

This result is identical to maximizing the number of degenerate arrangements of an energy level e_i with $n(e_i)$ particles and g_i degeneracies i.e.

$$(n(e_i) + g_i - 1)! / \{ n(e_i)! (g_i - 1)! \} \text{ subject to the constraints } ((7a, 7b)). \quad ((10))$$

One may see that even though $n(e_i)!$ tries to remove information because it is in the denominator as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $(n(e_i) + g_i + 1)!$ increases the permutation value with increasing $n(e_i)$.

To arrange ((10)) in the form of a reaction balance problem one may consider maximizing ((10)). One then has the two terms (using Stirling's approximation):

$$\ln(n(e_i) + g_i - 1) \text{ and } -\ln(n(e_i)) \quad ((11))$$

This suggests a reaction balance form of:

$$n(e_i) / \{ n(e_i) + g_i + 1 \} \text{ instead of } n(e_i) \text{ in } ((1))$$

$$\text{One has: } \ln\left\{ \frac{n(e_i)}{n(e_i) + g_i} \right\} = (e_i - u)/T \quad ((12))$$

$$\text{for } g_i \gg 1. \text{ This yields: } n(e_i) = g_i / \{ \exp((e-u)/T) - 1 \} \quad ((13))$$

This means that reaction balance may be written as:

$$E_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \text{ and}$$

$$n(e_1) / \{ n(e_1) + g_1 \} \cdot n(e_2) / \{ n(e_2) + g_2 \} = n(e_3) / \{ n(e_3) + g_3 \} \cdot n(e_4) / \{ n(e_4) + g_4 \} \quad ((14))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a certain functional form may be linked with certain information. In particular, we consider the problem of elastic scattering with $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. E_i is a piece of information as is $n(e_i)$. A third piece of information is $n(e_1)n(e_2)=n(e_3)n(e_4)$. This leads to the association: $\ln(n(e_i)) = -e_i/T$ ((A)) and the solution $n(e_i)=C \exp(-e_i/T)$. Thus the exponential function is associated with certain information. We further note that e_i is the result of $\{d/dn(e_i)\} e_i$

$n(e_i)$ and so is linked with a maximization process with $e_i n(e_i)$ being a constraint. What should be maximized? We argue that $n(e_i) = Np(e_i)$ for large N . Given probabilities, one may create large N trial runs (i.e. microstates). Each has the same probability (because e_i appears $Np(e_i)$ times), but all of the microstates form a set of permutations. Thus the probability of a microstate is: $1 / \{ \text{number of permutations} \} = 1 / \{ N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)! \}$. This may be maximized with the constraint $\text{Sum over } i e_i n(e_i)$. Thus the three information pieces leading to $\exp(-e_i/T)$ maps directly to a maximization of $\ln(n(e_i)!)!$ with e_i from $\exp(-e_i/T)$ appearing in the constraint.

This idea may be extended to the grand canonical partition function with the weight $\exp(-(E-uN)/T)$. E may be written in terms of single particle $e_i n_i$ and $N = \text{sum over } i n_i$. For a given e_i , one still has a sum over n . Thus something special occurs within a single e_i state. It seems one tries to place as many particles within such a state (in the boson case) using $\exp(-(e-u)/T)$ as a product weight per particle i.e. $\text{Sum over } n=0 \text{ to infinite } \exp(-(e-u)n/T)$. The form $\exp(-(e-u)/T)$ is linked with the maximization of factorials of $\ln((n(e_i) + b) !)$. These in turn are linked with permutations? What permutations should exist within a single e_i ? There should not be any unless there is degeneracy such as momentum direction with constant magnitude degeneracy, for example. In such a case, one may maximize the number of degenerate permutations within e_i and find a result which matches the grand canonical approach. This approach encourages more particles within a state e_i . Thus $n(e_1)n(e_2) = n(e_3)n(e_4)$ no longer holds, but enhancement factors appear because there is a higher probability to scatter into a state with more particles than fewer.

References

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